

Kinetics of Hydrolysis of *N,N'*-Di-*p*-methoxyphenylphosphorodiamidic Chloride

V. SAHNI and S. PRABHA*

School of Studies in Chemistry, Jiwaji University, Gwalior-474 011

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Hydrolysis of *N*-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)phosphorodiamidic chloride has been studied in the acid region, 0.01 to 8.0 M HCl at 40° (acetic acid-water 20%, v/v). Ionic strength effect differentiates two contributory forms, the neutral as well as the conjugate acid form, the former being reactive as the zwitterionic form. Rates are reduced on adding DMF and DMSO. The frequency factor (10^{13}) being on the borderline of uni- and bimolecular mechanisms also favours the zwitterionic form, so that the transition state may be possible with dispersal of +ve charge. The value of *E* (15.05 kcal mol⁻¹), however, requires a bimolecular hydrolysis, although involving a short-lived transition state. Effect of metal ions is used to strengthen specific acid catalysis suggested by neutral electrolyte effect studies. A maximum at 4.0 M acid and other parameters used in comparative kinetic data favour P—N bond cleavage for this diester. Coplanarity of *p*-CH₃O substituent with the rest of the matrix is highlighted by the highest magnitude of rates due to acid catalysis in the series of diesters examined.

THE hydrolysis of a diester with C—N—P linkage has been pursued to account for the most suitable pathway(s) depending upon the presence of the neutral (modified) and the conjugate acid species. The polar neutral form has been suggested in the case of aminophosphates (monoesters mainly) by Chanley and Feageson¹. So the objective was to find out their presence and contribution in the diesters. It may be worthwhile to mention that a detailed kinetic study led us to postulate the zwitterion for *N*-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)phosphorodiamidic chloride.

Experimental

N-(*p*-Methoxyphenyl)phosphorodiamidic chloride was prepared by stirring *p*-anisidine and PCl₅ (1 : 1) in benzene, for about 7 h. It was recovered by repeated precipitation with ammonia and HCl, m.p. 146° (Found : C, 53.8 ; H, 6.80 ; N, 7.95 ; P, 9.49. C₁₄H₁₆N₂PO₂Cl calcd. for : C, 51.45 ; H, 4.90 ; N, 8.57 ; P, 9.49%).

All chemicals used were either of AnalaR or G. R. (S. M.) quality. Deuterium oxide was procured from Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Trombay and its isotopic purity as reported was >99.4%.

Kinetics of hydrolysis of *N,N'*-di-*p*-methoxyphenylphosphorodiamidic chloride has been investigated in the acid range 0.01-8.0 M HCl in 20%

(v/v) acetic acid at 40°. The progress of the reaction was followed by estimating the rate of appearance of inorganic phosphate². The concentration of the diester was maintained at 5×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ throughout the study, except when its concentration effect was determined.

Results and Discussion

The first order rate constants for the hydrolysis of *N*-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)phosphorodiamidic chloride increases with the increase in acid molarity upto 4.0 M, at which a maximum appears. After this, the rates decrease gradually. This decrease in rates, after the maximum, is attributed either to negative electrolyte effect or decrease in water activity, or both.

In order to determine and distinguish between the operative reactive forms, ionic strength studies³ have been carried out using appropriate proportions of sodium chloride and HCl. The first order rate coefficients have been summarised in Table 1. The diamidic-chloride does behave like other diesters and gives three linear curves (Fig. 1), which on extrapolation, give intercepts of different magnitudes. It is noticed that, these values when further modified, correspond to a linear curve, indicating constant contribution of the neutral form (Fig. 2). Thus, the rates *via* the neutral form for this diester are expected to be rather constant, but the overall

TABLE I—OBSERVED AND CALCULATED RATES FOR HYDROLYSIS OF *N*-(*p*-METHOXYPHENYL)-PHOSPHORDIAMIDIC CHLORIDE AT 40°

Sl. no.	Acid <i>M</i>	10 ³ <i>k_N</i> ⁺ min ⁻¹	10 ³ <i>k_H</i> ⁺ <i>C_H</i> ⁺ min ⁻¹	<i>k_e</i> Found/ (Calcd) × 10 ³ min ⁻¹
1.	0.01	3.98	—	3.84 (3.98)
2.	0.10	3.98	0.35	4.42 (4.33)
3.	0.50	3.98	1.62	5.83 (5.60)
4.	1.00	3.98	2.89	6.21 (6.87)
5.	2.00	3.98	4.62	4.67 (8.60)
6.	3.00	3.98	5.53	5.63 (9.51)
7.	4.00	3.98	5.89	9.76 (9.87)
8.	5.00	—	5.87	4.88 (4.11) ^a
9.	6.00	—	5.63	3.72 (3.46) ^a
10.	7.00	—	5.24	2.67 (2.76) ^a
11.	8.00	—	4.77	1.85 (2.09) ^a

^an is 1 in equation (5).

Fig. 1. Hydrolysis of di-*p*-anisidine phosphate at constant ionic strength at 40°: (O) 1, (Δ) 2 and (□) 3 μ.

Fig. 2. Hydrolysis of di-*p*-anisidine phosphate via conjugate acid and neutral species: (O) 5 + log *k_N*⁺ and (Δ) 5 + log *k_H*⁺.

magnitude of these is quite high and significant. Here the 2nd empirical term of Debye-Hückel equation⁴ for the calculation of rates via the neutral form is reduced to

$$5 + \log k_N = 5 + \log k_{N^+} \quad (1)$$

Further, this neutral form has been considered to participate better as a modified zwitterionic form so that equation (1) may be further modified as

$$5 + \log k_{N^+} = 5 + \log k_{N^+O} \quad (2)$$

However, the neutral form is accompanied by the conjugate acid form. For the latter, the rates rise with the increase in acid molarity. However, slopes of these linear curves, i.e. acid-catalysed rates decrease with the decrease in μ, indicating -ve ionic strength effect on the acid-catalysed species. This form is, however, reactive in the entire acid range, although the rates decrease after 4.0 *M*. These specific acid-catalysed rates are, therefore, based on the equation,

$$5 + \log k_{H^+} = 5 + \log k_{H^+O} - b'_{H^+} \cdot \mu \quad (3)$$

The latter parameter is a negative quantity because the slope of the linear curve in modified plot (Fig. 2) is also -ve. These bimolecular rates have been modified into unimolecular rates by multiplying them with the concentration of acid so that

$$\log k_{H^+}C_{H^+} = \log k_{H^+O} + \log C_{H^+} - b'_{H^+} \cdot \mu \quad (4)$$

On the basis of equations (2) and (4), rates have been specifically calculated and are found to agree closely with the observed rates (Table 1) especially in the low acid region. Thus, both modified neutral and conjugate acid forms of this diester are present and are contributory.

The lowering in rates after the maximum, i.e. 4.0 *M*, is attributed to both, negative ionic strength effect and decrease in water activity. The number

of water molecules involved is only one at each acid molarity, and this has been determined by applying the modified form of Brönsted-Bjerrum equation,

$$k_{e_{oalod}} = k_{H^+O} \cdot C_{H^+} \exp. b_{H^+} \mu (a_{H_2O})_n \quad (5)$$

where, n is the number of water molecules involved. Concepts of Hammett⁶ and Zücker-Hammett⁷ leading to slopes, zero and 1.19, are favourable for the participation of water in the rate-determining step. Parameters of Bunnett⁸ ($w=11.09$ and $w^*=3.31$) emphasise that water acts as a nucleophile too, in addition to the above behaviour. Value of $\Phi(1.65)$ based on the plot of Bunnett and Olsen⁹, postulates further that water acts as a proton-transfer agent, when the proton attaches to N of the C—N—P linkage.

Arrhenius parameters¹⁰ (Table 2) being nearly the same, before and after the maximum, account

TABLE 2—ARRHENIUS PARAMETERS FOR HYDROLYSIS OF *N*-(*p*-METHOXYPHENYL)PHOSPHORODIAMIDIC CHLORIDE IN AQUEOUS HYDROCHLORIC ACID

HCl <i>M</i>	E kcal mol ⁻¹ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	A s ⁻¹	$\Delta S^\ddagger$ e.u. (JK mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta G^\ddagger$ kcal mol ⁻¹ (kJ mol ⁻¹)
3.0	15.05 (62.96)	7.11×10^{12}	-26.99 (126.8)	23.28 (23.28)
5.0	13.22 (55.31)	1.91×10^{12}	-32.53 (102.0)	23.40 (23.38)

for the absence of maximum protonation. Both E (energy of activation) and E-based $\Delta S^\ddagger$ (entropy of activation) favour the presence and participation of water molecule in the formation of a transition state. The frequency factor is just near the border line of uni- and bi-molecular reactions. However, all the other Arrhenius parameters postulate a bimolecular mechanism.

The hydrolysis *via* the neutral form by both uni- and bi-molecular modes will result in creation

of charges, so that the rates are enhanced by a changeover from less to more polar solvent. However, in the present study, the results are just the opposite. Thus, it is possible that both the reactive forms exist as charged structures initially and this then is dispersed during a bimolecular attack. According to qualitative theory of Hughes and Ingold¹¹ this dispersal may be decided by solvent effect studies and it results in the decrease in rates to some extent by an increase in the polarity of the solvent.

In order to confirm the above, solvent effect study has been made using solvents of different polarities. At low acid molarity (0.1*M*), increase in the percentage of a protic solvent, like acetic acid, brings about a lowering in rates. This lowering suggests the formation of a transition state, in which there is either a reduction or dispersal of charge. Use of dipolar aprotic solvents¹², like DMF and DMSO, also brings about a lowering in the magnitude of rates. Such an effect is possibly due to its strong interaction with the hydrogen ions of the acid present (HCl) as well as its association with water molecules. In the former, there is depletion of H₃O⁺ ions due to the formation of DMFH⁺ like species, so that the net effect is a decrease in velocity of hydrolysis in this phase.

All the above results and reasonings either suggest an altogether different pathway or require the existence of the neutral form as its cationic state, *i.e.* zwitterion in the acid range, hydrolysing by a bimolecular pathway. Such a structure will bring about a dispersal of the +ve charge, so that when solvents are varied as above, the rates may be lowered to some extent. Solvent-isotope¹³ effect studies made in D₂O lead to lowering in rates, suggesting a specific acid-catalysed reaction.

The rate of hydrolysis is lowered¹⁴ when different electrolytes are used in the low as well as high acid region. In the acid range, the reaction requires the presence of electrophilic species, like H⁺. The following order of decreasing strengths in water has been observed for a series of electrolytes: H⁺ > Na⁺, K⁺. The decrease in rates due

TABLE 3—COMPARATIVE KINETIC DATA FOR HYDROLYSIS OF SOME DIAMIDATES *via* THEIR CONJUGATE ACID SPECIES

Sl. no.	Diesters (C—N—P)	Temp. °C	$k_e \times 10^3$ min ⁻¹	Maxima <i>M</i>	E kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ e.u.	Molarity	Fission	Re.
1.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ -aniline	50	<i>d</i>	1.0	11.40 ^a	38.66	2	P—N	15
2.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ -aniline	50	8.42	5.0	9.15 ^e	37.29	2	P—N	16
3.	<i>p</i> -Br-aniline	90	27.50	4.0	9.15 ^b	55.98	2	P—N	17
4.	<i>p</i> -Cl-aniline	90	19.40	4.0	9.15 ^b	56.78	2	P—N	17
5.	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ -aniline	98	2.58	3.5	16.61 ^b	31.90	2	P—N	18
6.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -aniline	98	0.06	2.0	14.64 ^a	44.91	2	P—N	19
7.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O-aniline	40	9.76	4.0	15.05 ^b	26.29	2	P—N	This work
8.	<i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅ -aniline	98	18.57	4.0	5.72 ^b	70.55	2	P—N	20

a,b,c — At 1.0, 3.0 and 5.0 *M*, respectively. d — Data not available.

Chart 1.

to different electrolytes, like LiCl, NaCl, is in accordance with the reasoning that they act as soft electrophilic centres as compared to the aquated ion. This nature makes the hydrolysis difficult, because the leaving group ($\text{H}_3\text{CO}-\text{Ph}-\text{N}^+\text{H}_2$) is comparatively of the harder type.

The concentration effect study was also carried out at low as well as at high acid molarities. Rates are found to be insensitive to concentration changes. Thus the reaction is proved to be of the first order type. The second reaction partner, water, in this bimolecular reaction is always present in excess, so that it is better to refer the rates as pseudo-first order rates.

Existence of an isokinetic relationship¹⁴ ($\beta = 187.5^\circ$) and comparative kinetic data (Table 3) showing similarity in behaviour suggest P—N bond cleavage for this diester. P—N bond rupture is also justified by the formation of a suitable *p*-anisidine molecule during hydrolysis. The maximum reactivity of the present diester requires participation of the *p*-MeO group in one way or the other. Since the ester has been shown to involve the modified neutral form, *i.e.* the zwitterion in the acid region upto 4.0 M, the acid catalysis leading to highest rates allows the stabilisation of the +ve charge by the *p*-MeO group (+M). It also requires the coplanarity of the *p*-MeO substituent with the site of protonation (NH) *via* the aryl matrix. The order of acid catalysis as seen from Table 3 can be

shown as: $p\text{-CH}_3\text{O} > p\text{-CH}_3 > p\text{-Br} > p\text{-Cl} > p\text{-OC}_2\text{H}_5 > m\text{-NO}_2 > p\text{-NO}_2$.

On the basis of the above discussion, it may be possible to postulate the following plausible routes of hydrolysis in the acid range *via* the two reactive forms (Chart 1).

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